

Цифровой инструментарий в рейтинговой системе комплексной оценки знаний студентов вуза

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Key words: rating system, comprehensive assessment, VUCA-world, digital instruments, “end-to-end” technologies, higher educational establishment.

Резюме: В статье предпринята попытка охарактеризовать и систематизировать цифровой инструментарий, а также «сквозные» цифровые технологии, используемые в рейтинговой системе комплексной оценки знаний студентов опорного вуза. Актуальность исследования обусловлена необходимостью дальнейшей цифровизации высшего образования в России, внедрения новых Интернет-технологий (ИТ) для усовершенствования контрольно-измерительных процедур, а также повышения конкурентоспособности специалистов на рынке труда. Автор акцентирует внимание на широком выборе отечественного цифрового инструментария и его доступности для участников образовательного процесса.

Abstract: The paper attempted to characterize and sum up digital instruments as well as “end-to-end” technologies used in the rating system of comprehensive knowledge assessment of students of a flagship higher educational establishment. The research topicality is proven by the need in further digitalization of higher education in Russia, introduction of new Internet technologies (IT) to upgrade the testing and assessment procedures and to increase the competitiveness of specialists in the labour market. The author draws the attention to a wide range of domestic digital tools and their availability for participants of the learning process.

[**Evseev A.B.** Digital tools in the rating system of comprehensive knowledge assessment in students of higher educational establishment]

Introduction

Despite tense situation in the world today, the ongoing rapid development of new technologies leads to constant changes in the structure of the Russian economy, affecting all areas of our lives. A constant increase in the number of technologies and a change in the speed of their appearance, quality, value and volume of

information, production and business processes, communications, a sharp increase in the amount of data - these are the main characteristics of the so-called VUCA-world in which we live today (VUCA is short for Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity). In spite of the sanctions inflicted by the Western countries, new markets and goods regularly appear, thus, causing the social landscape change. As a result, new channels of interaction are emerging; social space is being re-marked in a new way. Due to the sufficient number of domestic IT developments, a ban on the commercial use of some foreign software from January 2025 will not, in our opinion, affect the availability of digital tools in education, in particular, higher education. The Internet has a whole arsenal of digital technologies of the Russian segment which are successfully used in the educational activities today. Let us view in more detail at least some of them applied in the rating system for a comprehensive assessment of the knowledge of university students.

Peculiarities of the rating system for a comprehensive assessment of the knowledge at Vladimir State University

The rating system for the comprehensive assessment of student knowledge (RS) was introduced at Vladimir State University by order of the rector in May 2013. RS is a complex system of step-by-step assessment of the level of mastering by a student of the Major Professional Academic Programme of Higher Education (MPAP HE) in relation to other students on an equal footing. Among the tasks of the RS are:

- increasing the motivation of students to actively and uniformly master the MPAP HE through a high differentiation in the assessment of their educational work;
- obtaining operational information about the quality and effectiveness of training;
- obtaining personal data on the educational achievements of students for their encouragement;
- achieving a high level of organization of the educational process of the university;
- stimulating regular independent work of students.

When organizing the educational process with the use of RS,

students have an opportunity to:

- perceive the need for regular and systematic work on the assimilation of educational material based on knowledge of their current assessment in each discipline and its changes due to untimely or incomplete assimilation of the material;

- clearly understand the system of assessments in various disciplines;

- timely assess the state of their work on the study of the discipline, the implementation of all types of teaching load before the start of the examination period;

In turn, such a training system allows the teaching staff to:

- timely and fully monitor the progress of mastering the discipline by the whole group and each student, in particular;

- timely make adjustments to the organization of the educational process based on the results of ongoing monitoring;

- accurately and objectively put the final grade in the discipline, taking into account the intermediate results;

- provide a more accurate gradation of the assessment (a 100-point system instead of a five-point one).

All knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the process of studying the discipline are evaluated in points. For each discipline, the scores are summed up within the semester and recorded in mark sheets after the first and second intermediate certification, as well as the final assessment.

When studying the discipline, intermediate and final assessments are provided. The purpose of intermediate assessment is to evaluate the quality of mastering educational programmes by students upon completion of individual stages of training. The maximum amount of points scored by a student in the discipline (part of the discipline read during one semester) is 100. Based on the points scored, students' progress in the semester is determined with the following grades: “excellent”, “good”, “satisfactory” and “unsatisfactory” for disciplines ended in exams or credits with an assessment on the following scale:

- from 100 to 91 points (“excellent”) The theoretical content of the course was mastered successfully the necessary practical skills of working with the mastered material were shaped without any

gaps, all the assignments provided for by the syllabus were successfully completed, the quality of their performance was estimated by a number of points nearing the maximum.

- from 90 to 74 points (“good”) The theoretical content of the course was fully mastered without any gaps, some practical skills in working with the material studied were insufficiently completed, all assignments provided for by the syllabus have been completed, the quality of performance of none of them has been assessed with the minimum number of points, some types of tasks have been completed with errors.

- from 73 to 61 points (“satisfactory”) The theoretical content of the course has been partially mastered but the gaps are insignificant, the necessary practical skills for working with the mastered material are basically shaped, most of the assignments provided for by the syllabus have been completed, some of the completed tasks, may contain errors.

- 60 points or less (“unsatisfactory”) the theoretical content of the course is poorly mastered, the necessary practical skills were not shaped, the completed assignments contain gross errors, additional independent work on the course material will not lead to a significant improvement in the quality of the assignments.

The maximum amount (100 points) gained by a student in the discipline to be ended with the exam is made of the two components. The first component is the assessment by the teacher of the results of the student's educational activities in the study of the discipline during the semester (in the amount of no more than 60 points). The second component of the assessment in the discipline is the assessment of the student's knowledge at the exam on a 40-point scale. Points that prove the student's progress in the discipline are collected by him during the entire period of study for the study of certain topics and the performance of certain types of work. The specific assignment of the number of points scored for certain topics and types of work is carried out by the leading teacher in the discipline and depends on the structure of the discipline. This consolidation should be discussed at a meeting of the chair and reflected in the syllabus of the discipline. When choosing the criteria for assessing the student's success of the discipline, it is mandatory to

take into account as follows: the completion of the syllabus in terms of lectures, practical and laboratory classes; performance of classroom and (or) extracurricular control and other written work provided for by the syllabus. The teacher who monitors the progress in the discipline is obliged to bring to the attention of the students the criteria for their certification in the framework of the intermediate and final control of progress at the first lesson. If, based on the results of three intermediate assessments (in the test week), the total number of points scored by the student in the discipline is less than 20, then the student is not allowed to take the exam in this discipline. It is allowed to assign additional “bonus” points to the student for general activity in studying the course, preparing an essay, speaking at a conference, and so on. The sums of points scored by the student based on the results of each assessment, including bonus points, are entered by the teacher into the special mark sheet stored at the dean's office (Regulations on the rating system for comprehensive assessment of the knowledge of students at the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education “Vladimir State University named after Alexander Grigorievich and Nikolai Grigorievich Stoletov” (VISU), 2021).

Role of digital instruments in the rating system of the higher educational establishment

According to the Development Programme of Vladimir State University for 2021-2030, the policy in the field of digital transformation of a higher educational institution is aimed at creating a system for training personnel for the digital economy, supporting the development of promising “end-to-end” digital technologies and projects for their implementation, improving management efficiency, provision of educational services and scientific activities through the introduction of digital technologies and platform solutions. Moreover, it adds to the creation of a modern high-speed infrastructure for storing, processing and transmitting data, ensuring the stability and security of its operation, the introduction of “end-to-end” digital technologies, such as neurotechnology and artificial intelligence (AI), virtual and augmented reality technologies (VR/AR), distributed registry technologies, quantum technologies,

new production technologies, robotics and sensor components, wireless communication technologies. The main goal of the digital transformation policy is to upgrade the basic processes at the university owing to digital technologies; introduce state-of-the-art technologies into the educational process, integrate online platforms into the environment of the university; introduce personalized educational paths and courses; implement new possibilities of space and formats. The University is to:

- shape the information space, taking into account the needs of the university in obtaining high-quality and reliable information;
- improve the reliability characteristics of the digital infrastructure on an ongoing basis;
- use and develop various educational technologies, including distance, e-learning, in the implementation of educational programmes;
- develop and implement partnership programmes of educational institutions of higher education and Russian high-tech organizations, including the improvement of educational programmes;
- develop the electronic interaction technologies along with the possibility of interaction without the use of information technologies;
- create management and monitoring systems based on information and communication technologies in all areas of the university;
- active introduction of “end-to-end digital” technologies in educational process and their use in the system of comprehensive assessment of students' knowledge (VISU Strategic Development Program until 2016-2030).

At the present stage of development of higher education in the country, the use of an arsenal of digital products in RS is extremely necessary. It allows to motivate students to work more fruitfully in mastering academic disciplines. In addition, it helps to unlock their inner potential, increase efficiency during training, and digital opportunities. Today it is impossible to imagine the educational process without the use of virtual classrooms/whiteboards, cloud storage, digital portfolio, online tests and quizzes, video

conferencing. Let's take a closer look at each of these promising digital tools.

Virtual classrooms/boards

There is a number of applications for creating virtual classrooms for immersive learning and supervision. An increased involvement is achieved through more productive activities, revealing the creative potential of each student, visualizing teamwork and the personal contribution of each team member, and increasing the dynamism of content. The general principles of functionality include:

- group work in a single space;
- synchronous and asynchronous learning;
- autonomous and group work;
- connectivity with any source on the network and with the contents of cloud storages;
- a wide possibility of use in project activity.

This toolkit includes Miro, SBoard. Among the key advantages of these digital platforms are a variety of built-in tools, a wide selection of templates in English, an intuitive interface, and free access for educational institutions. They play an important role in the RS of the university, as they allow to optimize the control process by reducing paperwork.

Cloud storage

The teacher gets an opportunity to provide students with large amounts of data: articles, sets of illustrations, videos, music, etc. All of them are safely stored as a cloud collection. Accumulated over the years, the materials are now stored without any threat of the loss. Also, cloud storage is a great opportunity to save teaching staff from the paperwork, the need to print and store control and measuring materials. This toolkit includes such free services as Mail.ru cloud (up to 8 GB of free memory), Dropbox (up to 2 GB), OneDrive (up to 5 GB), iCloud (up to 5 GB), Google Drive (up to 15 GB).

Digital portfolio

This is a necessary tool in a comprehensive system for assessing the knowledge and achievements of students. During the study, the database accumulates information about the disciplines mastered, the award of nominal scholarships, diplomas, certificates

etc. Thanks to the digital portfolio, a student can electronically apply for financial assistance and an increased state academic scholarship, send applications for an academic leave or create a request for an individual study schedule. Accumulating information about success in studies and science, as well as the results of participation in competitions and contests, the electronic portfolio allows the student to keep track of achievements and, in the future, can serve as a hint in which direction to successfully develop. In addition, a digital portfolio can be a good way to demonstrate the competences of a university graduate. By posting documents with information about their practical experience, graduates get an opportunity to show the employer their commitment and desire to work in their chosen field. A student's digital portfolio allows to objectively assess personal and professional growth, see the dynamics of the development of certain disciplines, improve control over the assessment of the formation of competencies. The possibilities of shaping a personal portfolio of a student of VISU are still under development and will be available in the personal account on the official website of the university in the near future.

Online tests and quizzes

Online quizzes have become quite popular in educational institutions. They allow you to diversify the educational process, systematize the control of knowledge, provide constant feedback with students. Free digital tools available in Russia include Udoba, Online Test Pad, Moodle, Google Forms, Mentimeter, Kahoot!, Quizizz, Master Test. In a comprehensive assessment of knowledge, these platforms allow teachers to unify the control and measurement materials, making the assessment more impartial.

Videoconferencing

It means an essential digital tool for remote work. It is a platform for conducting online training events for employees, students of promotional webinars for clients, remote collaboration and discussions with partners. Thanks to videoconferencing services, it became possible to work remotely during the pandemic. Among the services are VK Zvonki, Skype, Zoom, Pruffme, TrueConf. Although the above platforms have their drawbacks, however, in the rating system they add to the parties' mobility, time management,

efficiency increase and strengthening of team ties.

Conclusion

Summing up the above, there is a wide range of digital instruments available for comprehensive assessment of students' knowledge in the domestic market today. The digital education offers new opportunities for higher professional education. There is a chance for making the education more personalized, getting instant feedback and active involvement of students into the educational process. The range of new patterns of mutual cooperation, innovative learning strategies is broadening. It adds to the increase in students' inner motivation, academic achievements and relieves "teacher-student" interaction.

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